

The Role Entrepreneurial Leadership Behavior to Engage the Civil Servant Performance

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 22, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: November 26, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Bureaucratic Culture, Entrepreneurial Leadership Behavior, Employee Performance</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5730643</p>	<p><i>The purpose of this study is to examine and analyze the relationship between attitude, subjective norms and interest factors on entrepreneurial leadership behavior (ELB), and civil servant (ASN) performance with direct and indirect effect. Total respondents of this study is 86 ASN who work in the Government of Southeast Minahasa Regency. The data analysis technique used the Structural Equation Modeling PLS (SEM-PLS) method. The result of this study state, interest factors is influenced by three factors: attitudes, subjective norms, and perceptions of behavioral control. This study indicates that attitudes and perceptions of behavioral control significantly affect interest in ELB, and personal criteria do not considerably affect interest in ELB. Bureaucratic culture and interest in ELB have a significant influence on ELB. Power weakens the impact of ELB on ASN performance. ELB has a high contribution to the performance of ASN, namely 97.6%. It states that ELB is the answer in improving the performance of ASN in providing public services to achieve better government performance.</i></p>

Introduction

The increasingly rapid development in information technology is one of the triggers for accelerating various changes today. Change is unavoidable both in aspects of human life in general and in particular the government order. The paradigm shift of state administration from the theoretical foundations and the foundation of political epistemology to economics. The responsiveness of the public bureaucracy expressed by clients & constituent changes to society as a customer. Like, working following the will of the market (customers' wishes) and assumptions on employee & administrator motivation. Based on the experience of Europe, US, Australia, and New Zealand, as well as various other developed countries, in the last few decades has gradually promoted the concept of government management. Such as The British government uses the idea of the welfare state. The Japanese government uses the idea of "amakudari" which emphasizes the close relationship between the public and private sectors.

In Indonesia, Smart City systems have been implemented in Jakarta, Bandung, Makassar, Surabaya, Semarang, Yogyakarta and Denpasar. This is evidence of the progress of a city because the leadership spirit possessed is an entrepreneurial spirit. Various views on the paradigm shift in state administration manifested by multiple developed countries, it turns out that the point is focused on the concept of commercial or entrepreneurship. The concept of entrepreneurship is the central concept for the progress in Dubai city, namely focusing on Entrepreneurial Leadership Behavior (ELB). Thus, ELB is a concept that deserves to be understood and adopted by various developed countries and Indonesia. ELB is a form of innovative leadership, a pillar of the strength of economic growth, as a popular leadership style that is significant, strong, predictor & able to improve performance. Several studies agree that ELB is a unique form of leadership from general leadership behavior (e.g., (Renko et al. 2015; Leitch and Volery 2017; Gupta, MacMillan, and Surie 2004). This is because entrepreneurs have differences from HR managers. ELB is considered relatively the same as the soul of young people (Ensley et al., 2006). From the various studies, the phenomenon of leadership success in the government confirms that the spirit of entrepreneurial behavior can be adopted in carrying out leadership in government (e.g., Zhu and Wang 2011; Morris Jr 2014). The entrepreneurial-based leadership model starting from the values and characteristics of entrepreneurship, is a form of quality leadership because it has succeeded in change and strategic steps in various fields in achieving the expected goals.

According to (Akob et al., 2020; del Carmen Pérez-Fuentes et al., 2021; Mappamiring et al., 2020), work motivation is influenced by three variables i.e., attitudes, subjective norms, and perceptions of behavioral control. These three variables affect the welfare and eventually become a behavior. The behavior will not occur without interest. In the interest variable, there is a perception of behavior that controls all treatment efforts that are good to do and which are not suitable to be avoided, which are adjusted to subjective norms. The perception

of State Civil Apparatus (ASN); control behavior that seeks to provide good service will affect the interest in behaving. If this concept of thinking is adopted in how ASN works, it is expected to contribute to good performance and eventually lead to good government performance.

The government is carrying out its duties based on the Regulation of Republic of Indonesia Number 32/2004 concerning regional government. In the negotiations, it is regulated regarding the proper implementation of regional autonomy. It is necessary to measure performance based on the implementation of the government in that regional autonomy. The government's performance is related to achieving the ultimate goal of translating national development into long-medium and short-term development plans (Mustafid, 2017). Government Agency Performance Accountability Report (LAKIP) is a government agency accountability that contains government performance achievements.

Southeast Minahasa Regency is a division of South Minahasa Regency in 2007, based on the researcher's initial observation that LAKIP is evidence of commitment from all current ranks in improving the effectiveness of performance reporting but is still ranked B, from 2018, 2019, and 2020. Critical issues until In 2020 LAKIP is still predicated B, which should change to BB predicate because, since 2018, the government has been trying to utilize various digital technology facilities and provide performance allowances to improve the quality of ASN performance so that in answering this problem it can be assumed that a good solution is with efforts to implement entrepreneurial leadership behavior in the Southeast Minahasa Regency government. The uniqueness of the Southeast Minahasa Regency in the journey of the Southeast Minahasa Regency government has always been at the forefront. The official application of south minahasa government use the electronic-based Performance Application (i.e., E-Kinerja), to improve the professionalism of ASN in playing instruments as public servants, which is oriented towards creating a quality, accurate, transparent, and accountable government service system. This indicator is a form of progress for the Southeast Minahasa Regency, but there are gaps found in the wheels of government. Provision of Regional Performance Allowances, which should motivate work morale, being honest and responsible in the use of the budget, but there are still cases of corruption which tend to be assumed as a factor in the decline in government performance. The results of initial observations stated that there was bad behavior, personal clashes, ASN who did not fit into a team, there was no transparency, there was no clarity of roles, and there were rumors of negative stigma in the work environment.

Referring to Government Regulation Number 53/2010 concerning Civil Servant Discipline, it was found that ASN did not come to work for an extended period. So that, according to the government of the Southeast Minahasa Code of Ethics Council, David Lalandos there were three people who were intended to commit serious violations. Moreover, the trial decided the honorable dismissal of two ASN and the dishonorable dismissal of one ASN. This decision was taken to enforce ASN discipline within the Southeast Minahasa Regency. The explanation of the perception of behavioral control above can be stated that how can it be expected to create a generation of quality leaders if in conditions like the above the ASN is unable to control the desire to behave or the leader's inability to form good bureaucratic cultural values. So that ultimately it must lead to dismissal, compared to understanding the importance of ELB. What is expected in the Southeast Minahasa Regency Government is achievement-oriented, has perseverance and grit, has strong determination, likes to work hard, is energetic, and has initiative. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to address some of the main issues that need to be studied, for example: Does attitude, subjective norms, perception of behavioral control and bureaucratic culture have a significant effect on ELB. Of course, this study is expected to contribute to the development of science, especially in the field of human resource management and in particular to be able to contribute to the implications of developing the civil service system in the state civil apparatus.

Terminologically, entrepreneurship is the ability to create, seek and take advantage of opportunities to attain ideal goals. Entrepreneurship can create business activities (Monferrer et al., 2015; Yohan et al, 2013), requiring creativity and innovation to find something different from before and contribute to society, the process of finding, recognizing (Arshed, 2017). Taking advantage of new opportunities, the process of producing new products, modifying existing activities, not looking for risks but looking for opportunities (Wilczynski&Schanz, 2021; Drucker, 1999). Willpower through unusual ways, leadership, business skills, innovation, creativity, production method, proper timing, modification. new management concept, standardization in achieving something ideal, i.e., new market and customers, adequate monetary reward, complete satisfaction, community contribution, economic improvement and progress of a country. Entrepreneurial behavior is an interdisciplinary concept. Entrepreneurial behavior will contribute to economic growth through leadership, innovation, job creation, competition, productivity, and new industrial formats (Elrehail, 2018; Lukoschek et al., 2018). According to the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor, entrepreneurial behavior acknowledges the authenticity of a new business when there is an opportunity, where opportunity is the primary condition even if it is not enough. The initiation of entrepreneurial behavior occurs from building capabilities, motivation, and skills to take advantage of opportunities to establish new companies. Likes in the ELB principles in HR development. That ELB concept based on: First, cognitive Ambidexterity (prioritizing predictive logic and creative logic in decision-making. Second, Social, Environmental, and Economic Responsibility and Sustainability; directs the creation of potential synergies on social, environmental and economic values as sustainable responsibilities,

utilizing the understanding of the social context to achieve goals with action effective. Third, Self and Social Awareness have meaning makes more effective decisions in uncertain and unknown circumstances and self-understanding of the awareness of achieving goals influenced by the surrounding environment.

Main Components of the Theory of Planned Behavior and ELB such as attitude. Attitude is defined as the totality of affection that a person feels when refusing or accepting an object. Behavior is measured in a procedure on two poles of an evaluation scale, namely bad or good, rejecting or agreeing, belief in behavior is displayed because of a helpful evaluative reaction (Heikkilä et al., 2017). The attitude component, explains that there are three aspects of the attitude component, e.g., cognitive aspects, which are related to symptoms regarding thoughts in the form of processing, experiences, and beliefs as well as individual expectations about objects or groups. It is in the form of knowledge, ideas, or thoughts based on information related to objects. Affective aspects, namely in the form of processes related to certain feelings such as fear, malice, sympathy shown to specific things. Conative part, namely the method of tendency the tendency to act on an object, for example, the tendency to give help, distance themselves and so on.

The second subject in ELB relationship with TPB is Subjective norms which mean a person's view of the beliefs, which will later affect interest by considering whether to behave or not behave. The idea of social pressure to act or not is more emphasized on subjective norms (Elhoushy, 2020; Giampietri et al., 2018). Normative beliefs form subjective norms and trusted referents' motivation to assess whether the social environment affects behavior. It can be evaluated on subjective norms. The above understanding can be concluded that what is meant by subjective norms is a function of trust due to social pressure that agrees and wants to have an interest in behaving in particular objects. So that, the components of subjective norms are divided into two, namely normative beliefs and motivation to comply. According to Ajzen & Fishbein (2012), a person's ability to behave refers to one's perceptions, which indicates a person displays behavior or not depends on perceived behavioral control. Perception of behavioral control is formed from two components. The component is control belief, which is a person's perception of how complex behavior appears, which comes from his perception of the difficulties, risks, and challenges involved if he wants to issue a behavior. Second, perceived power talks about a person's perception of whether or not he can bring up behavior by considering the difficulties, risks, and challenges that accompany it (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1976). Based on the above understanding, it can be concluded that what is meant by perceived behavioral control is a function of a person's ability to control his behavior. Or the proposition of having an interest in conduct is divided into two components: control belief and perceived power.

One of the factors that influence behavior as a motivational one is called interest which indicates the strength of a person trying to behave or the extent of one's efforts to act. The greater a person's prediction for behavior, the stronger the interest in behavior. Based on the above understanding, the appeal can be completed as a function of desire/willingness that is firm, strong, and hard on attitude. Perception of control behavior and subjective norms as a particular behavior, which can be observed directly or through the conclusion of a test. Behavior is the result of interaction/a response/stimulus from individuals to adapt to their environment to survive is expressed as behavior. The primary motivation to behave is survival's main reason as humans' immediate impulse to act. An indication of an individual's readiness to perform a particular behavior is considered a direct antecedent of the behavior. It is based on attitudes towards the behavior, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control with each predictor, weighed for importance concerning the population of interest. Behavior is an individual response that can be observed in a particular concerning a particular target.

Bureaucracy Theory

The following briefly describes several theories of bureaucracy put forward by experts, starting from the Classical Bureaucracy Theory of Karl Marx, Max Weber's Bureaucracy Theory, and the Theory of David Osborne and Ted Gaebler (Modern Bureaucracy). The theory that reaches the stage of development is historical materialism and the achievement of state ideas, especially capitalist or Marx's theory. The organization sees the bureaucracy being used, guaranteeing rights and protecting the interests of the bourgeoisie. The state's independence still exists only because the wealthy owners of the modern classes are still in power and cannot be shifted because no other group can control society. Marx explained that the bourgeoisie remained in force in the role of bureaucrats so that the system was still chaotic without any vast improvement of the whole order. In Indonesia, based on the Decree of the Minister for Empowerment of State Apparatus number 25/2002, the government has stipulated a policy on developing a work culture of the apparatus. The main points of work culture values in the state apparatus are commitment and consistency to the vision, mission, and goals of the organization, authority & responsibility, sincerity and honesty, integrity and professionalism, leadership and exemplary, togetherness and group dynamics, accuracy and speed, rationality and emotional intelligence, determination, and firmness, discipline, and regularity of work, courage and wisdom, dedication and loyalty, enthusiasm and motivation, perseverance and patience, fairness and openness, science and technology. According to Nohe & Michaelis, (2016); and Stone (2019), the concepts of leadership and power have a close

correlation. There are often some opinions that say that leadership is identical/equal to power. Indeed, a leader can use his power as a tool to achieve his personal or group goals, but in essence, leadership and power have differences. Power in an organization is a strength or a threat. Power is the capacity to produce impact the potential to influence others, the ability to defend oneself from the influence of others (Meiyani& Putra, 2019; Cooke et al., 2018; Skoludova& Brodsky, 2015).

Employee Performance Concept

Performance is an achievement of work in an organization based on the authority and responsibility given to achieve organizational goals legally. By the law and moral/ethical performance of employees, the main thing that must be considered is the improvement of improvements through an assessment of the quantity, quality, and efficiency of services to encourage employees to understand better the needs of the people served to improve public services (Elçi et al., 2012; Haerani et al., 2020). According to Afsar et al., (2015); Huang & Wang (2011), employee performance is closely related to work effectiveness. Performance as an effort to achieve work results through adequate policies, procedures, and organizational environmental conditions. The intended performance criteria are personal ownership issues related to government values, to bring consequences for employees to have a concern for customers, the application of customer-focused values, which has implications for organizational effectiveness (Józsa, 2017; Lee & Trimi, 2021). Performance is the result of work that appears through the management process or an organization as a whole, where tangible evidence of the process must be concretely measurable. The definition refers to the performance of employees who must have work results after carrying out their duties based on their responsibilities within a certain period and can be measured and proven concretely in achieving the organization's goals legally.

Performance measurement is an essential tool to evaluate the value of the work of a person, group, or organization. According to Sedarmayanti (2001), performance measurement is feedback from the value sacrificed with the results achieved. Thus performance is essential to measure the level of achievement made by individuals, groups, and organizations. Therefore, an assessment of performance needs to be carried out continuously. It is known that the sacrificed output with the results achieved can then determine the direction and goals that are considered essential to be carried out. Indicators in measuring performance proposed by Khan & Rasheed (2015); Olson et al (2018) are as follows: Quality (the extent to which the process or results of implementing activities are close to perfection or in other words approaching the expected goals), quantity (the amount produced in work activities, timeliness (the extent to which an action can be completed on time as desired by paying attention to coordination with other outputs, as well as the time available for others), cost-effectiveness (the extent to which use of organizational, human, capital, technology, and material resources that can be maximized to achieve the highest results or reduce losses from each unit of resource use), need for supervision (the extent to which an employee can carry out a job function without requiring maintenance by a supervisor or supervisor for me prevent and minimize unwanted actions), interpersonal impact (the extent to which employees maintain self-esteem, good name, and cooperation among colleagues and subordinates).

Method

Samples Criterium

This research is research using a non-experimental quantitative analytical approach (cross-sectional study) and survey. The variables in question include Employee Performance, Bureaucratic Culture, Attitudes, Subjective Norms, Perception of Behavioral Control, Interest in Entrepreneurial leadership behavior, Entrepreneurial leadership behavior, and Power in Organizations (Power). The research location was conducted in the Southeast Minahasa Regency Government of North Sulawesi Province. The population in this study uses all members of the Southeast Minahasa ASN with total 86 respondents (See. Table 1) Furthermore, the source of data collection as shown in table 2. The data collection methods used are questionnaires (See. Table 3). The instrument was given to the respondents using a Likert scale technique of five points to measure the research variables (1 = strongly disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = neutral, 4 = agree, 5 = strongly agree). The data testing technique uses the following methods: (1) Nomological validity. It is necessary to evaluate the questionnaire question items by a competent panel of experts (Joseph F Hair, 2011). This study focuses on research patterns from the perspective of broaden-built theory and organizational theory so that the survey structure follows the pattern of the two theories. Apart from that, the approach of this study uses a PLS-SEM-based quantitative analysis method.

Table 1. Respondent Data

Demography	Total	%
Gender		

- Men	46	54
- Women	40	47
Age (Years old)	35	65
Latest Education Level		
- Senior High school	8	9,3
- Diploma	10	11,7
- Bachelor	58	67,4
- Magister	10	11,6
Length of work	Average >10 years	75

Table 2. Informant Source

No.	Department	Informant Source	Gender	
			Men	Women
1.	Environmental Agency	3	1	2
2.	National Political Unity Agency	3	2	1
3.	Research & Development Agency	2	2	-
4.	Department of Youth and Sports	2	2	-
5.	Department of Public Health	3	2	1
6.	Department of Transportation	2	-	2
7.	Department of Industry, Cooperatives and Trade	3	2	1
8.	Department of Education	3	2	1
9.	Department of Fisheries and Maritime Affairs	3	1	2
10.	Department of Archives	2	-	2
11.	Department of Public Works Service	6	4	2
12.	Department of Settlement Service	2	2	-
13.	Department of Social Services	3	3	-
14.	Department of Transmigrant Service	3	3	-
15.	Department of Family Planning Service	3	3	-
16.	Community Empowerment Agency and Village Government	3	2	1
17.	Food Security Agency	3	2	1
18.	Regional Finance Agency	6	2	4
19.	Department of One-Stop Integrated & Investment Service	3	1	2
20.	Department of Population and Civil Registration	4	2	2
21.	Department of Human Resources Development	3	-	3
22.	Regional Planning and Development Agency	3	1	2
23.	Department of Communication and Information	4	2	2
24.	Department of Agriculture	4	2	2
25.	Civil service police Unit	4	-	4
26.	Regional Disaster Management Agency	3	-	3
27.	Child Protection and Empowerment Service	3	3	-
<i>Total</i>		<i>86</i>	<i>46</i>	<i>40</i>

Measurement

The measurement of this study uses several dependent variables and their measurement items such as: Measurement of attitude variable using a questionnaire consisting of ten questions consisting of behavior belief, namely 5 questions and evaluation of behavioral belief, namely 5 questions, of the ten questions that are valid, namely the practice of leadership behavior according to community needs, government models that responsive, a new government model, very profitable and in accordance with applicable laws. Measurement of subjective norms variable using a questionnaire consisting of ten questions consisting of norms beliefs five questions and motivation to comply five questions, of the 10 ten questions there are six valid questions, namely in conducting entrepreneurial leadership, the respondent gets support from co-workers, superiors, community, family and in accordance with beliefs. Measurement of perceived behavioral control variable using a questionnaire consisting of ten questions consisting of five control beliefs and five perceive power control questions, out of ten valid questions four questions, namely practicing ELB because there is support from various parties, rules that make it easier, have an impact on performance, for the welfare of the people and respondents practice it because they

feel there is support. The measurement of bureaucratic culture variable uses a questionnaire consisting of six questions, one invalid question, so that the remaining five valid questions remain. Measurement of ELB interest using a questionnaire consisting of seven questions consisting of a frequency of three questions and positive recommendations four questions, of the seven valid indicators are four valid questions, namely respondents consider the practice of entrepreneurial leadership behavior as ASN, for regional progress, has a positive impact, recommends to colleagues and superiors. Measurement of entrepreneurial leadership behavior (ELB) and ASN performance variable using a questionnaire consisting of six questions. Measuring mediator power using a questionnaire consisting of five questions. In detail we illustrate the conceptual model of this study as shown in Figure 1.

We also used SPSS to measure the normality of the variables with the Kolmogorov-Smirnov method. The normality test results show that the data is normally distributed (Asymp. sig > 0.12). The second stage of testing measures the outer model on SmartPLS, i.e., loading factor > 0.60 (Fornell & Larcker, 1981; Hair et al., 2014); inner-model testing (i.e., Cronbach alpha, composite reliability, and AVE provided that each test value is > 0.60) (Chin, 1998); measurement of goodness of fit model by evaluating data testing criteria, i.e., Standardized Root Mean Square Residual and Normed Fit Index (SRMR < 0.80, NFI > 0.90) (Henseler et al., 2016; Bentler & Bonett, 1980). d_{ULS} and d_G with the criteria original value (saturated model > estimated model). Then test the coefficient of determination and F-test (R-Square and F-test). The final research testing stage is hypothesis testing using the constant bootstrapping method with chi-square ($n = 86$).

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Therefore, in connection with what we have described in the literature review section and variable measurement, the hypothesis in this study refers to several points such as:

- H1: Attitude is an item that can become an antecedent that has a positive relationship in developing the behavior intention antecedent factor variable.
- H2: Subjective norm is an item that can be an antecedent that has a positive relationship in developing the behavior intention antecedent factor variable.
- H3: Perception of Behavioral Control is an item that can be an antecedent that has a positive relationship in developing the behavior intention antecedent factor variable.
- H4: All behavioral intention antecedent factors are positively and significantly related to entrepreneur leadership behavior
- H5: Bureaucratic culture is positively and significantly related to entrepreneur leadership behavior.
- H6: ELB is positively and significantly related to performance.
- H7: Power in the organization moderates the positive relationship between ELB and performance.

Results and Discussion

Statistical Analysis

Table 3 explains that after several question items that do not meet the applicable standards are removed from the statistical analysis to get a standard value of AVE > 0.6. The results of data analysis showed that all the items that made up the variables were declared valid with an AVE value > 0.50. In addition, all constructs of research variables have met the reliability test, both assessments based on the value of Cronbach alpha and composite reliability. According to Hair et.al., (2010: 710) a reliability value higher than 0.7 can be considered very good and ideal. Likewise with the composite reliability criteria assessment the results are also as good as the Cronbach alpha value, where all the results of the assessors produce a composite reliability value higher than 0.7. The composite reliability measurement is consistent with an internal value greater than 0.6 and so if it is less than 0.6 then it is not reliable. The reliability of the external absolute standard loading indicator with a value of 0.7, the value shown in the table above is above 0.7, then composite reliability is meeting the absolute standard.

Table 3. Validity and Reliability Test

Variables	item	Loading Factor	AVE	CR	Cronbach Alpha	
Attitude	A1	0,760	0,510	0.837	0.756	
	A2	0,650				
	A3	0,800				
	A4	0,776				
	A5	0,684				
Subjective Norms	SN1	0,673	0,563	0.882	0.838	
	SN2	0,859				
	SN3	0,779				
	SN4	0, 890				
	SN5	0,705				
	SN6	0,544				
Behavior Perception	Control	BCP1	0,802	0,579	0.836	0.755
		BCP2	0,710			
		BCP3	0,616			
		BCP4	0,712			
Behavior Antecedent Factor	Intention	BIAF1	0,776	0,509	0.857	0.800
		BIAF2	0,646			
		BIAF3	0,800			
		BIAF4	0,739			
		BIAF5	0,587			
ELB		ELB1	0,692	0.506	0.841	0.763
		ELB2	0,516			
		ELB3	0,730			
		ELB4	0,738			
		ELB5	0,780			
		ELB6	0,780			
Bureaucratic Culture		BC1	0,652	0,5165	0.841	0.763
		BC2	0,738			
		BC3	0,714			
		BC4	0,773			
		BC5	0,643			
Power in the organization		PTO1	0,730	0,559	0.841	0.763
		PTO2	0,584			
		PTO3	0,782			
		PTO4	0,767			
Performance		P1	0,708	0,525	0.834	0.739
		P2	0,621			
		P3	0,475			
		P4	0,700			
		P5	0,754			

Variables	item	Loading Factor	AVE	CR	Cronbach Alpha
	P6	0,765			
	P7	0,708			

Table 4 explains that the value of each item loading factor is already in its construct and does not experience cross-loading problems. These results indicate that the instrument items are different from other items, and it is concluded that each instrument item represents its constructor. It can also be stated that there is no multicollinearity between variables because each construct measures different things. And the instrument in this study has met the requirements of discriminant validity. In addition, Table 4 also interprets that explains that the value of each item loading factor was in its construct and did not experience cross-loading problems. These results indicate that the instrument items are different from other items, and it is concluded that each instrument item represents its constructor. It can also be stated that there is no multicollinearity between variables because each construct measures. Different things and the instrument in this study have met the requirements of discriminant validity.

Table 4. Discriminant Validity

Attitude	Subjective Norms	Behavior Control Perception	Behavior Intention Antecedent Factor	ELB	Bureaucratic Culture	Performance
0,773 0,636 0,797 0,742 0,601	0,679 0,864 0,782 0,888 0,695 0,534	0,799 0,702 0,817 0,718	0,761 0,612 0,790 0,749 0,636	0,707 0,780 0,762 0,750 0,753 0,754	0,641 0,730 0,774 0,781 0,653	0,766 0,554 0,666 0,758 0,808 0,766

Referring to the validity and reliability tests results in Table 5, it can be concluded that the research data is feasible to continue evaluating the structural model and testing hypotheses. Evaluation of the structural model / inner model test aims to predict the relationship between latent variables (Hair et al., 2010)—the inner model in SEM.PLS refers to the value of R Square (R^2) for endogenous latent constructs (Chin, 1998). The meaning of the determinant coefficient (R Square or R squared) as the contribution of the influence given by the exogenous variable to the endogenous R Square value is the determinant coefficient on the endogenous construct. According to Hair et.al., stated 0.75 (strong), 0.5 (moderate) and 0.25 (weak). The results of this study show that the R^2 value on the endogenous variable of employee performance is 0.917, the R^2 value of the endogenous variable of entrepreneurial leadership behavior is 0.965, and the R^2 value of the endogenous variable interest in entrepreneurial leadership behavior 0.999. Chin's The Role of Thumb / ROT to assess these results. Table 5 shows that if the value of R^2 then the evaluation of the structural model of each endogenous variable seems strong. Employee performance with a value of 0.917 can be interpreted that the ELB variable correlates with employee performance by 91.7%, while the rest are other variables. ELB endogenous variable with R^2 0.965 can be construed as work culture and ELB variables as determinants and correlates to ELB by 96.5% and the other variables. The endogenous variable of ELB interest with an R^2 value of 0.999 can be interpreted that the attitude and perceived behavioral control variables correlate with ELB interest but is dominated by the behavioral control perception variable with a total of 99.9% and other variables influence the rest.

Table 5. Structural Model Evaluation

Endogenous Variables	R^2	Result
Performance	0,917	Strong
ELB	0.976	Strong
Behavior Intention Antecedent Factor	0,999	Strong

Table 5 shows the beta coefficient and T-statistical values, so the test results for each hypothesis are as follows: H1 regarding Attitude is an item that can become an antecedent that has a positive relationship in developing the behavior intention antecedent factor variable with a value of the beta coefficient is 1.178 and t-value is 21.2. That is, H1 has a significant effect and is declared support. H2 states that subjective norm is an item that can be an antecedent that has a positive relationship in developing the behavior intention antecedent factor variable. The calculation results show the beta coefficient value -0.00199 and t-value 1.171. It means H2 has no effect and is not significant, and is declared unsupported. H3 states that the perception of Behavioral Control is an item that can be an antecedent that has a positive relationship in developing the behavior intention antecedent factor variable. The calculation result of Smart PLS2.0 software has a beta coefficient value of -0.184 and at-value of 3.917. This shows that the behavioral control perception indicator has a negative and significant effect on the interest in entrepreneurial leadership behavior. It means H3 has no effect and is substantial. H4 states that all behavioral intention antecedent factors are positively and significantly related to entrepreneur leadership behavior. The calculation results of Smart PLS2.0 software show a beta coefficient value of 0.60 and at-value of 7.36. This means that H4 has a significant effect and is declared to be supportive. H5 states the factor that Bureaucratic culture is positively and significantly related to entrepreneur leadership behavior. The calculation result of Smart PLS2.0 software shows that the path between entrepreneurial leadership interest and entrepreneurial leadership behavior has a beta coefficient value of 0.52 and the t-value of 4.59. This indicates that the indicator of interest in entrepreneurial leadership behavior positively and significantly affects entrepreneurial leadership behavior. This means that H5 has a significant effect and is declared effective. H6 states that ELB is positively and significantly related to performance. The calculation result of Smart PLS2.0 software shows that the path between entrepreneurial leadership behavior and employee performance has a beta coefficient value of 1.32 and at-value of 2.99. This shows that the indicators of entrepreneurial leadership behavior have a positive and significant effect on employee performance. It means H6 significant impact and declared support. H7 states that entrepreneurial leadership behavior factors affect performance with a power mediator variable. The calculation results of Smart PLS2.0 software show that the path has a beta coefficient value of -0.144 and at-value of 2.283. This indicates that entrepreneurial leadership behavior factors have a negative and significant effect on employee performance with power mediating variables. It means H7 is significant and weak.

Discussion

This study provides empirical evidence that attitudinal factors can affect the interest in entrepreneurial leadership behavior. This evidence is supported by ASN's assessment of the practice of entrepreneurial leadership behavior on behavioral items of belief, namely according to the community's needs, as a responsive model, as a new governance model, and following applicable laws. The ability to evaluate behavioral beliefs cannot be demonstrated. This is because ASN is still unable to properly assess the practice of entrepreneurial

leadership in each of the agencies/agencies they work. ASN believes that entrepreneurial leadership behavior is significant, but they have not been able to respond in the form of an evaluation into the elements of their work. The evaluative response as a form of reaction that is expressed because of the emergence of an attitude is based on an evaluation process within the individual that concludes the stimulus in the form of good or bad values. Positive and negative, pleasant or not, then crystallizes as a potential reaction to the attitude objective, which in the end, the attitude can evaluate the object.

The effect of attitude on interest is stated as one of the factors that significantly positively impact interest in entrepreneurial leadership behavior. In this study, it turns out that attitude is also an antecedent or predictor of the formation of interest in entrepreneurial leadership behavior in ASN. In testing the validation of the subjective norm variable measurement instrument using two components, namely normative beliefs and motivation to comply following Fishbein and Azjen theory, concerning ELB in this study, personal norm variables are perceptions or views of other people's beliefs in affect the interest of ASN in doing ELB does not have a significant effect. The subjective norm of ASN is not a reference in the interest in behavior. This is because people's opinions do not cause the beliefs/perceptions/views of ASN without role models, but based on the results of the motivation to comply questionnaire from ASN in their work to do what is suggested by colleagues who are believed to be role models. Skills and have expertise from him. The question of normative beliefs about faith and belief should support a person doing better and quality work because it contains religious values. Still, the fact turns out that normative beliefs do not keep it concerning entrepreneurial leadership behavior. The truth is that there are still ASNs in the Southeast Minahasa Regency Government who have positions as Heads of Divisions who do not yet have the ability and expertise to follow their primary tasks, namely officials who are not following their educational background. This was found in an office where the ASN with a background as a Midwife but whose place of work was at the Food Defense Agency. As well as a pharmacist was found working at the Family Planning Service and an Economics as the Head of Pharmacy. In terms of this expertise, that gives confidence to subordinates so that the distribution of work can be completed in a timely and collaborative manner. The prominent role of leadership is to influence others to achieve goals by applying entrepreneurial leadership behavior. There will be fundamental changes in the public sector in increasing efficiency and effectiveness and the ability to innovate. The awards received and the village innovation exchange activities prove that the bureaucratic culture in terms of increasing innovation in the Mitra Regency Government is getting better, so entrepreneurial leadership behavior has also been seen and implemented. To solve all existing problems, the Ministry of State Apparatus Empowerment-Bureaucracy Reform in Indonesia made the Grand Design a roadmap for world-class bureaucracy characterized by quality public services with efficient and effective governance.

The principle of entrepreneurial leadership behavior is a more economical, efficient, and effective commercial principle that has been applied in various developed countries so that the study of the public service sector through measuring the performance of the local government will be better. It is known that leadership and power are related, and it is often said that leadership is the same as power. A leader with his ability can be used to achieve goals individually or in groups, but this is inversely proportional to the results of this study because power in organizations is more directed at the dependency factor and entrepreneurial leadership behavior avoids the dependency factor. Providing performance allowances is the same as provincial performance allowances only as an effort to achieve the desire to get awards, but the professional values are not adequate, so that employee performance is still lacking and has an impact on organizational performance.

Conclusion

Planned behavior theory (PBT) is a theory that explains consciously about human behavior on the basis that humans behave considering the availability of all information. PBT is used to imagine and explain behavioral interests as a fact of everyday life. The relationship between attitude and evaluation of interest will describe certain results in the form of behavior. Beliefs related to personal views about truth are subjective norms. Perceived behavioral control shows belief control which includes the individual's view of the opportunity to do something. This is very important to evaluate all resource capabilities to be successful.

As in the research novelty model, it can be explained that the results of the PBT implications state that ASN's interest in entrepreneurial behavior is determined by behavioral interest, this behavioral interest is influenced by two variables, namely: attitudes and perceptions of behavioral control. The researcher's initial understanding of the moderating variable of organizational power will strengthen entrepreneurial leadership behavior in achieving ASN performance, but the results actually weaken it, so from several interviews with respondents, the researchers found the causes of these obstacles, namely:

- a) Operating System Procedure

Operating System Procedure (SOP), SOP as a benchmark in doing work, so that whatever will be done must be based on standards otherwise it will have a bad impact. The advantage of SOP is that there is unity of direction in carrying out work, but there are events that occur unexpectedly, so there is a need for a signal of creativity, dare to take risks when facing something unexpected, because there are many opportunities related to decisions for better service. However, because it is limited to SOPs, this causes delays in public services and has an impact on low performance.

b) Main Task System

In each of the Main Job Duties of each ASN at the bottom / last, everything states that each ASN always performs other work tasks based on orders from superiors. This is what causes the element of coercion to follow what the boss wants, so that work is not attached to the position but only to please the boss. This is the obstacle to ASN's innovation power in carrying out every job.

c) Control System

The bad impact of excessive supervision on ASN is discomfort in the space for implementing work. If you make a mistake, there is always an attempt at punishment, but it doesn't give you the freedom to learn from your mistakes and find something behind them. Even though every creator has mistakes and repeatedly learns to finally find high creativity.

This research has practical implications for the Southeast Minahasa Regency government in terms of improving employee performance to adopt entrepreneurial leadership behavior. In adopting the concept of entrepreneurial leadership behavior, it needs to be socialized starting from the attitude, namely the practice of entrepreneurial leadership, especially behavior that leads to meeting the needs of the community, responsive government and in accordance with applicable laws.

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